

Research Article

Present Status of the Level of Agricultural Mechanization available for Cassava Processing Operations in Oyo State of Nigeria

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Abstract

Cassava is a crop that is attached to many importance in Nigeria. The present administration of the Buhari-Osinbajo led government has shown great willingness to diversify the nation's economy in which agriculture is one of the sectors considered for this diversification of the economy. Processing of cassava calls for great attention considering the deteriorating nature of the crop after been harvested for 2 – 3 days. For this reason, the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin in April 2018 conducted a National Mechanization survey exercise in Oyo State to find out the present level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operation so as to know which area of the processing operation aspect of cassava that calls for urgent attention in the State. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey exercise in the State. Survey results revealed for the nine (9) cassava processing operations involved showed that cassava peeling and washing operations were almost dominated by manual processing method in all the cassava processing units visited in the State. A total of 65.20% was recorded for manual processing method for the nine (9) processing operations involved for cassava. It was also noted that a total of 20% was recorded for mechanical processing method for the nine (9) cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering and milling operations contributed to this figure. This 20% value obtained for machine involvement for the processing of cassava in the State calls for urgent attention of the Oyo State government to increase the number of cassava processing machines used for the processing operations of cassava in the State. Cassava processors in the State should be

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

encouraged by the State government through the provision of loan facility in which they can use to procure cassava processing machines for use in boosting their cassava processing operations.

Keywords: processing, cassava, method, processor, unit, manual

Received: 21 April 2019

Accepted: 09 July 2019

Introduction

Cassava is an important crop in Africa. It survives in poor soils, has a high yield of carbohydrates and good resistance to pest infestations, diseases and drought. According to NextGenCassava (2013), cassava roots are processed and eaten by 500 million people a day in Africa where it is a staple for 40% of the population. Taiwo and Fasoyiro (2015) reported that cassava grows well in west, east, central and South African countries. Cassava is a versatile crop; all parts of the plant including its root have been processed into a number of products.

Cassava plays a particularly important role in the agriculture of developing countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. It is a food security crop which serves both as subsistence and cash crop to poor resource farmers. Cassava tubers and the various products hold an important position in Nigerian economy and also in its gross domestic product, which also is found common to Ghanaian economy (Taiwo and Fasoyiro, 2015).

Nigeria produces cassava more than any other country in the world (Ezedinma et al., 2007; Knipscheer et al., 2007). Its production increased from 34 million metric tonnes a year in 2002, to 54 million metric tonnes (Elemo, 2013; FAO, 2015). Nigeria only accounts for 0.001% of the world cassava export market (Tijani and Thomas, 2011). The promotion of cassava for export in Nigeria is important to increase foreign exchange earnings. For this reason, there is need to investigate the level of our readiness in promoting the export of cassava products to other countries. In order to do this, there is need to conduct a National Mechanization survey exercise among agro-processors into cassava processing operations in Oyo State of Nigeria. This paper tends to discuss the outcome of the survey exercise carried out in Oyo State of Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out in Oyo State. It is an agrarian community located within the derived savannah vegetation of Nigeria. The crops grown in this vegetation include cassava, maize, melon, groundnut, cocoa, kola, oil palm and cashew. According to Akinyemi (2018), Oyo State is in the south-west of Nigeria with its capital in Ibadan. The state lies between latitudes 6° 55' and longitudes 8° 45'N and longitude 2° 50' and 3° 56'E. It is bounded in the north by Kwara State, in the east by Osun State, in the south by Ogun State and in the west partly by Ogun State and partly by the Republic of Benin. Oyo State covers approximately an area of 28,454 km² and is ranked 14th by size. The state has 33 Local Government Areas. Ibadan is the third largest metropolitan area (by population) in Nigeria after Lagos and Kano. It has an area of 629 km² and a population of 7,840,900 (NPC, 2006). Oyo has five broad group divisions; Ibadans, Ibarapas, Oyos, Oke-Oguns and Ogbomoshos. Oyo State is homogenous, mainly inhabited by the Yoruba ethnic group who are primarily agrarian but have a predilection for living in high-density urban centers. The indigenes mainly comprise the Oyos, the Oke-Oguns, the Ibadans and the Ibarapas, all belonging to the Yoruba society. Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Oyo State. Oyo enjoys a similar dual climate condition to the rest of the south-western states, with a rainy season and a dry season. The climate is equatorial, notably with dry and wet seasons with relatively high humidity. The dry season lasts from November to March while the wet season starts from April and ends in October. Average daily temperature ranges between 25°C (77.0° F) and 35°C (95.0° F), almost throughout the year. According to Fawole and Thomas (2011), the climate in the State favours the cultivation of crops like maize, yam, cassava, millet, rice, plantains, cocoa, palm produce, cashew etc.

Research Methodology

The study involves the use of primary source of data to obtain relevant information needed for this study. The structured questionnaires used for this study was designed by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin. The structured questionnaire was used to embark on a National Mechanization survey exercise in Oyo State. The survey was carried out in April 2018 using competent and experienced staff of the Oyo State Agricultural Development Programme office that are familiar with the terrain of the State. A total of 834 questionnaires were taken to Oyo State for the survey exercise by one of the key Technical staff of the Centre (NCAM) for the purpose of organizing a one day induction workshop programme for the enumerators to be used

for the survey exercise. These enumerators were trained on how the structured questionnaires would be filled by the respondents. The NCAM survey questionnaires were administered in the 33 Local Government Areas of the State. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey. During the course of carrying out the survey, NCAM in their own part monitored the survey activity by paying personal visit to some of the target groups in the different Local Government Areas of the State as a way to ensure that information provided by the enumerators were genuine. A total of 786 questionnaires were returned back to NCAM as filled questionnaires. The returned questionnaires were thoroughly scrutinized one after the other by the Technical staff who conducted the Induction Workshop programme so as to ensure that the proper information needed from the survey carried out were properly provided for use during data capturing. After data capturing, the questionnaires were sorted out by separating those into agro-processing occupation from other occupations contained in the structured questionnaire. A total of 356 agro-processors were found in Oyo State as 190 of them were noticed to fall into cassava processing operations. The 190 questionnaires meant for those into cassava processing operations were specifically used for this study.

Statistical Tool

Data obtained from the 190 respondents into cassava processing operations in Oyo State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation.

Results and Discussion

The summary of the data computed for the agro-processors into cassava processing operations in Oyo State is presented in Table 1. It is good to note from Table 1, that a total of 356 agro-processing units were visited in the State out of which 190 agro-processing units representing 53.37% were into cassava processing operations. It can be deduced from Table 1, that there are 9 cassava processing operations captured in the structured questionnaires designed by NCAM for use in the National Mechanization survey exercise carried out in Oyo State. Arranging the outcome of those that picked manual processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, results obtained revealed that we have a total of 184 representing 96.84% of the cassava processing units visited adopt manual processing method for peeling of cassava. A total of 174 representing 91.58% of the cassava processing units visited

Table 1. Results of Level of Agricultural Mechanization obtained for Cassava Processing operations in Oyo State

Processing operations	Level of Agricultural Mechanization					
	MN		MC		UD	
	A	B (%)	A	B (%)	A	B (%)
Peeling	184	96.84	6	3.16	Nil	Nil
Washing	174	91.58	12	6.32	4	2.10
Grating	67	35.26	107	56.32	16	8.42
Chipping	103	54.21	26	13.68	61	32.11
Dewatering	83	43.69	86	45.26	21	11.05
Drying	142	74.74	8	4.21	40	21.05
Garification	128	67.37	27	14.21	35	18.42
Milling	67	35.26	67	35.26	56	29.48
Bagging	167	87.89	3	1.58	20	10.53
Total	1115 (65.20%)	N/A	342 (20.00%)	N/A	253 (14.80%)	N/A

Keynote: A = Frequency count; B = Frequency count in its percentage value; MN = Manual operation; MC = Mechanical operation; UD = Undecided; N/A = Not applicable

Note: Total No. into agro-processing activity in Oyo State = 356; Total No. of agro-processors into cassava processing operation = 190; Percentage of agro-processors into cassava processing = 53.37%.

engage in the manual processing method of washing cassava. A total of 167 representing 87.89% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of bagging cassava. A total of 142 representing 74.74% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of drying cassava. A total of 128 representing 67.37% of the cassava processing units visited adopt manual

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 ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

processing method for the garification of cassava. A total of 103 representing 54.21% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of chipping cassava. A total of 83 representing 43.69% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of dewatering cassava mash. A total of 67 representing 35.26% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of grating and milling of cassava, respectively. A total of 65.20% was recorded for manual processing method for the 9 processing operations involved for cassava.

Likewise, arranging the outcome of those that picked mechanical processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, we have a total of 107 representing 56.32% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for grating cassava. A total of 86 representing 45.26% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of dewatering cassava mash. A total of 67 representing 35.26% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of milling cassava. A total of 27 representing 14.21% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for the garification of cassava. A total of 26 representing 13.68% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for chipping cassava. A total of 12 representing 6.32% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for washing cassava. A total of 8 representing 4.21% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for drying cassava. A total of 6 representing 3.16% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for peeling cassava. A total of 3 representing 1.58% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for bagging cassava. A total of 20% was recorded for mechanical processing methods for the 9 cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering and milling of cassava contributed to this figure.

It can also be seen from the analysis carried out as shown in Table 1, that peeling and washing operations of cassava is almost done through manual means in the 190 cassava processing units visited in Oyo State. The adoption of mechanized cassava operations can only be seen in the areas of grating (56.32%), dewatering (45.26%) and milling (35.26%) operations. Data captured for those cassava processing units visited that picked undecided for their unit operation was not considered for discussion in this study as all discussion were based on those that choose between manual and mechanical means of processing cassava. For record purpose, a total of 14.80% was

recorded for those that picked undecided in 8 of their unit operations as presented in Table 1.

Conclusion

In order to determine Nigeria's readiness to promote the export of cassava products to foreign countries, a National Mechanization survey exercise was carried out in April 2018 in Oyo State of Nigeria. Investigation revealed that in almost all the cassava processing units visited in the State adopt manual processing method for peeling and washing of cassava. It was also noted that 56.32%, 45.26% and 35.26% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for grating, dewatering and milling of cassava, respectively. However, the total amount of 20% obtained for the involvement of machines used in the nine processing operations involved for cassava is indeed low for a State like Oyo State. The Oyo State government is hereby called upon to encourage cassava processors on the use of cassava processing machines for boosting cassava processing operations in the State. The State government can come in by assisting these cassava processors with the provision of loan facility in which they can use to procure cassava processing machines for use in their various organizations. Nigeria can only be food sufficient if government embraces the use of agricultural machineries and equipment in boosting agricultural productivity as this will go a long way in reducing the billions of Naira spent on yearly basis in importing food in feeding the nation's ever-teeming population.

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